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Large Scale Pesticide Multiresidue Methods in Food Combining Liquid Chromatography- Time-of-Flight Mass Spectrometry and Tandem Mass Spectrometry

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ABSTRACT

Liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) and liquid chromatography time-of-flight mass spectrometry (LC-TOFMS) are powerful and complementary techniques that can independently cover the majority of the challenges related with pesticide residue food control. The sequential combination of both systems benefits from their complementary advantages and assists to increase the performance and to simplify routine large scale pesticide multiresidue methods. The proposed approach consists of three stages: (1) automated pesticide screening by LC-TOFMS; (2) identification by LC-TOFMS accurate mass measurements; and (3) confirmation and quantitation by LC-MS/MS. We have developed a fast comprehensive (identification/confirmation + quantitation) automated screening method for 100 target pesticides in crops. In the first stage, a set of data including m/z accurate mass windows (within 20 mDa width) and retention time is obtained (using a standard solution containing all the targeted pesticides) in order to build the automated screening procedure, which is created automatically by assigning retention time and the m/z mass window for each target pesticide. Samples are then analyzed, and the method enables the screening and preliminary identification of the species first by retention time and m/z mass window, followed by subsequent identification (only if positive results) by LC-TOFMS accurate mass measurements. After that, final confirmation of the positive findings using two MRM transitions and accurate quantitation is performed by LC-MS/MS using a hybrid triple quadrupole linear ion trap (QqLIT) mass spectrometer. In addition, the use of this QqLIT instrument also offers additional advantageous scanning modes (enhanced product ion and MS³ modes) for confirmatory purposes in compounds with poor fragmentation. Examples of applications to real samples show the potential of the proposed approach, including the detection of nonselected “a priori” compounds as a typical case of retrospective evaluation of banned or misused substances.

INTRODUCTION

Current analytical methodologies applied to pesticide residue food control are based on the concept of “target analysis” where liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) in the selected reaction monitoring mode (SRM) is a powerful technique, particularly considering the high number of new non-GC amenable compounds.¹⁻⁵ However, this approach, with the perspective of around 800 compounds present on the market, requires food control laboratories to maintain very big stocks of different standards, standards solutions, as well as matrix-matched standards that have to be checked very frequently to evaluate their stability or quality, in order to comply with quality control guidelines.⁶ This fact dramatically reduces the throughput and productivity of the laboratory and constitutes, for most of the routine laboratories, a task difficult to tackle with, due to the necessary investments, time and personnel. On the other hand, in the current monitoring programs developed, between 30 and 60% of the samples assayed are free of pesticides and in the rest of samples involving positive findings, the residues detected are restricted in most cases to a small number (e.g., 80 compounds) of frequently applied compounds and therefore detected compounds.

Therefore, the practical “target analysis” approach applied in many routine laboratories on pesticide residue control basically consists of selecting a list of around 100-150 of GC and LC amenable compounds by using the established EU or FDA priority lists combined with any other information related with agricultural uses in their region. It means that the majority of the low frequency or misused (nonpriority) compounds are typically out of an extensive control and their detection is by chance or is based on extra information or extra analysis work. Obviously this approach can be enlarged to over 800 compounds to cover the majority of the pesticides, but the costs in time and money are only feasible for very few and big laboratories and when the cost per analysis does not represent any limitation. Dozens of methods would be required to monitor for 800-900 pesticides because multiresidue methods using both GC and LC with MS detection can cover about 600 of them, and the others typically need single class or single analyte methods. It is possible to conclude that effective pesticide residue food control is nowadays limited considering the international trade of food and pesticide formulations, the possibilities of very different agricultural practices in food production, and the serious limitations of the food control laboratories to evaluate such an amount of compounds routinely. A good example is the EU sanitary alert in January 2007 due to the detection of isofenphos-methyl in pepper, together with other illegal insecticides, when a retrospective evaluation of selected EU surveillance programs showed their presence during 2006 very often (over 20% of the suspected samples tested).⁷

For these reasons, in the field of food safety there is an obvious need of methods for the rapid and reliable screening of a large number of compounds, which could be able to provide binary response results (“yes/no” type) in terms of identification (presence/absence) as well as reliable quantitation (lower or higher than the maximum residue level (MRL) of a large number of target compounds (pesticides).

LC-MS/MS has become one of the fundamental techniques in multiresidue pesticide analysis. The development of LC-MS instrumentation allows for both the extension of the spectrum of target analytes determined in a single run and to realize a very fast analysis. The most common approach is based on LC-MS/MS using triple quadrupole instruments in the selected reaction monitoring (SRM) mode, where both the precursor/transition together with the retention time is defined by using pure standards “a priori”. The chromatographic run is divided in time windows containing a limited (10-30) number of transitions, with dwell times for each transition as little as 5 ms,¹⁻⁵ depending on instruments and manufacturers. One or two transitions are used per compound in order to confirm the findings of a positive result. Besides, it should be noted that the number of points collected across a chromatographic peak is a key determinant of data quality and affects the total number of scheduled MRM transitions per time window. The main advantage of LC-MS/MS is the

better sensitivity and lower limits of detection in order to enable control over the compliance of samples to MRLs set up for babyfood (from 0.003 to 0.01 mg kg⁻¹). High performance triple quadrupole instruments provide for detection of 100-150 compounds at the 1 µg kg⁻¹ level using this procedure. The number of compounds could be extended but only if a dedicated chromatographic optimization is accomplished or the dwell times and/or points collected across a chromatographic peak are lowered.

In contrast, LC-TOFMS has the ability to screen an unlimited number of compounds (theoretically). A time-of-flight mass spectrometer operates in full scan mode, and segmented analysis is not necessary (saving time in a chromatographic method development). LC-TOFMS is a cost-effective technique for performing routine accurate mass analysis of small molecules based on target databases.⁸ In addition to high mass accuracy, the benefits of TOFMS include medium resolution, wide mass range, and fast mass spectral acquisition speed with high full- scan sensitivity, all attributes being superior to those obtained with a scanned quadrupole. Previous data show that present TOF instruments provide absolute sensitivity at the low pg (injected) level, and although not as sensitive as triple quadrupole instruments operated in the SRM mode, they do provide the sensitivity needed to meet current food safety regulations.^{9,10} The number of pesticides that can be screened increases dramatically if an automated screening method can be used to look for the accurate masses of pesticides. For instance, preliminary studies were accomplished using accurate mass measurements and retention time information of pesticides, obtaining satisfactory results.¹¹ This approach has already been established in comprehensive toxicological urine screening and in analysis of drugs-of-abuse in seized street drug samples.^{8,12,13} Currently, a mass accuracy within 5 ppm can be routinely achieved, and confirmation via elemental composition/isotope pattern matching can be performed in an auto- mated fashion.

In this work, we propose a combined approach based on LC-TOFMS and LC-MS/MS analysis (Figure 1) for the comprehensive screening of priority (target) and nonpriority (low frequency and misused) pesticides. The method is based on three steps. First, a fast comprehensive automated screening method is performed with a unique LC-TOFMS run. Prior to analysis of real samples, this screening procedure is compiled with appropriate software. The screening method is created using a single standard solution containing all the pesticides, by assigning for each target pesticide its corresponding peak (retention time) and *m/z* accurate mass window. Samples are then analyzed and the method provides a preliminary identification of the species first by retention time and *m/z* mass window, followed by subsequent identification (if positive results) by LC-TOFMS accurate mass measurement (second step). Final confirmation and reliable quantitation is accomplished in the final step by LC-MS/MS analysis with two SRM transitions.

To perform the LC-MS/MS analyses of this work, we have used a hybrid triple quadrupole linear ion trap (QqLIT) instrument ("QTRAP"), which has been introduced recently.¹⁸⁻²¹ This instrument retains classical triple quadrupole modes for quantitative and qualitative analysis (SRM mode and neutral loss scan) and combines them with attractive modes for the confirmation of analytes or characterization of unknowns, including enhanced product ion mode, time delayed fragmentation, and MS³ with an ion accumulation capacity higher than a conventional three- dimensional ion trap analyzer. It means that the QTRAP analyzer can provide an improved sensitivity in these MS/MS studies. Compared to conventional triple quadrupole analyzers, this instrument also offers additional advantageous scanning modes (enhanced product ion and MS³ modes) for confirmatory purposes in compounds with poor fragmentation at low concentration levels, which cannot be confirmed easily by triple quadrupole instruments due to the high MRM ratio between the two transitions. This scenario proposed for priority (target) pesticides is combined with the ability of LC-TOFMS for the analyses of both nonpriority (low frequency and misused) pesticides and the possibility of recording a data file as a history of each individual sample allowing retrospective analyses without extra work. The identification criteria, quantitation capabilities, and effectiveness of the proposed comprehensive screening method have been evaluated with various food extracts.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Chemicals and Reagents. Pesticide analytical standards were purchased from Dr. Ehrenstorfer (Ausburg, Germany) or Riedel- de-Haen (Selze, Germany). Individual pesticide stock solutions (approximately 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) were prepared in pure methanol or ethyl acetate and were stored at $-18\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The selected list of compounds (Table 1) consists of the major classes of pesticides that are commonly used worldwide for treating crops of fruits and vegetables. HPLC-grade acetonitrile and methanol were obtained from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). Formic acid was obtained from Fluka (Buchs, Switzerland). A Milli-Q-Plus ultrapure water system from Millipore (Milford, MA) was used throughout the study to obtain the HPLC-grade water used during the analyses. PSA (primary-secondary amine) was obtained from Supelco.

Sample Treatment. Fruit and vegetables samples were purchased from different local markets. The employed procedure (so-called “QuEChERS”) described elsewhere²² comprised the following steps: a representative 15 g portion of previously homogenized sample was weighed in a 200 mL PTFE centrifuge tube. Then 15 mL of acetonitrile were added, and the tube was vigorously shaken for 1 min. After this time, 1.5 g of NaCl and 4 g of MgSO_4 were added, and the shaking process was repeated for 1 min. The extract then was centrifuged (3700 rpm) for 1 min. An amount of 5 mL of the supernatant (acetonitrile phase) was then taken with a pipet and transferred to a 15 mL graduated centrifuge tube containing 250 mg of PSA and 750 mg of MgSO_4 , that was then energetically shaken for 20 s. The extract was then centrifuged again (3700 rpm) for 1 min. Finally, an extract containing the equivalent of 1 g of sample per mL in nearly 100% acetonitrile was obtained. An amount of 2 mL of this extract was then evaporated to near dryness and reconstituted to 2 mL of 10% MeOH. Prior to LC-MS analysis, the extract was filtered through a 0.45 μm PTFE filter (Millex FG, Millipore, Milford, MA).

Liquid Chromatography. The separation of the pesticides from the whole fruit or vegetable extract was carried out using an HPLC system (consisting of vacuum degasser, autosampler, and a binary pump) (Agilent series 1100, Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA) equipped with a reversed phase C_8 analytical column of 150 mm \times 4.6 mm and 5 μm particle size (Zorbax Eclipse XDB-C8). An amount of 20 μL of the matrix extract was injected in each run. Mobile phases A and B were water with 0.1% formic acid and acetonitrile, respectively. The chromatographic method held the initial mobile phase composition (10% B) constant for 5 min, followed by a linear gradient to 100% B at 31 min. The flow rate used was 0.6 mL min^{-1} . A postrun period with a flow rate of 0.4 mL min^{-1} with the initial mobile phase composition was included after each run.

LC-Electrospray Time-of-Flight Mass Spectrometry. The HPLC system was connected to a time-of-flight mass spectrometer Agilent MSD TOF (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA) equipped with an electrospray interface operating in the positive ion mode, using the following operation parameters: capillary voltage, 4000 V; nebulizer pressure, 40 psig; drying gas flow rate, 9 L min^{-1} ; gas temperature, 325 $^{\circ}\text{C}$; skimmer voltage, 60 V; octapole dc 1, 37.5 V; octapole rf, 250 V; fragmentor voltage (in-source CID fragmentation), 190 V. LC-MS accurate mass spectra were recorded across the range 50-1000 m/z . Accurate mass measurements of each peak from the total ion chromatograms were obtained using an automated calibrant delivery system to provide the correction of the masses. The instrument performed the internal mass calibration automatically, using a dual-nebulizer electrospray source with an automated calibrant delivery system, which introduces the flow from the outlet of the chromatograph together with a low flow (approximately 10 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$) of a calibrating solution which contains the internal reference masses purine ($\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N}_4$ at m/z 121.050873) and HP-0921 ([hexakis-(1*H*,1*H*,3*H*-tetrafluoropentoxy)-phosphazene] ($\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6\text{N}_3\text{P}_3\text{F}_{24}$) at m/z 922.009798)). The instrument provided a typical resolution of 9500 ± 500 . The full-scan data recorded was processed with Applied

Biosystems/MDS Sciex Analyst QS software (Frankfurt, Germany) with accurate mass application-specific additions from Agilent MSD TOF software.

LC-Electrospray-Tandem Mass Spectrometry. The LC- MS/MS method was based on the same chromatography of the LC-TOFMS method, using a 3200 QTRAP MS/MS analyzer (Applied Biosystems, Concord, Ontario, Canada). This hybrid triple quadrupole/linear ion trap (QqQLIT) instrument is a mass analyzer in which the final quadrupole can operate as a conventional mass filter or as a linear ion trap (IT) with axial ion injection. The QqQLIT provides a linear accelerating (LINAC) high-pressure collision cell. It makes use of a field gradient to accelerate the fragment ions toward Q3, avoiding the “cross-talk” phenomena due to the residence time of those ions in the collision cell and, in consequence, ions of the same mass for multiple reactions present in Q3. In this way, the velocity of the ions through the cell is maintained, providing the capability for reducing MRM dwell times and the analysis of multiple components.

The analyses were performed using a TurboIonSpray source in the positive ion mode. The operation conditions were as follows: ionspray voltage, 5000 V; curtain gas, 10 (arbitrary units); GS1 and GS2, 50 and 40, respectively; the probe temperature, 200°C. Nitrogen served as the turbo gas and collision gas. Mass calibration and resolution adjustments on the resolving quadrupoles were performed automatically by using a 10^{-5} mol/L solution of poly(propylene glycol) introduced via a syringe pump and connected to the interface. MRM experiments were carried out for obtaining the maximum sensitivity for the detection of the target molecules. For confirmatory purposes, the use of enhanced product ion scan (EPI) and MS³ modes are also interesting features of this hybrid instrument without sacrificing sensitivity. The optimization of MS parameters (declustering potential (DP), entrance potential (EP), collision cell entrance potential (CEP) for precursor ions, collision energy (CE), and collision cell exit potential (CXP) for product ions) was performed by flow injection analysis (FIA) for each compound. Table 2 shows the values of the parameters optimized and the MRM transitions used for the confirmation and quantification of the selected pesticides. For confirmation of the studied pesticides, two MRM transitions were used, and for quantification, the most intense MRM transition was selected. Applied Biosystems/MDS Sciex Analyst software was used for data acquisition and processing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Automated Screening of Target Pesticides by LC-TOFMS Accurate Mass Measurements and Retention Time Information. The automated screening procedure enables the analysis of a large number of pesticides and degradates (i.e., 100–400) in food extracts using LC-TOFMS in the positive ion mode with full-scan accurate mass spectra. The main strength of the proposed approach is the theoretically unlimited number of compounds to be screened simultaneously at low concentration levels. In fact, no overlapping or interference was observed in the 100 studied compounds.

First, to construct the screening method, a solvent-based standard with the mixture of the 100 studied pesticides was analyzed. This run is used as a reference to create the screening method. The software processes the data file and automatically assigns peak and retention time to each compound/accurate mass window ((10 mDa) pair included in the method. The screening criteria consisted of (10 mDa accurate mass window, (0.25 min retention time window, and a minimum area count of 10 000 (approximately the typical area corresponding to approximately the LOD of a large number of the studied compounds). This threshold value could be used, for each individual pesticide, to give a binary response yes/no (presence/absence and/or, i.e., upper/lower of the MRL value). But, in our study the threshold value was chosen only to minimize false positives, due to the software, which otherwise perform the integration of peaks with a small S/N ratio.

In our study, the library comprised of exact monoisotopic masses for 100 multiclass pesticides. Once the screening method is established, real fruit and vegetable samples are injected. The sample analysis file is generated and introduced in the "Quantitation Wizard" of the Analyst software, and it yields the results for all the compounds included in the screening method. Each ion of interest in the database is searched and extracted (at the t_R window of interest) from the sample file in an automated fashion. An analysis of 100 pesticides takes from 2 to 5 min to be processed in a laptop, depending on the length of the file (a 30 min run analysis is approximately 80 MB). From the LC-TOFMS acquisition data, the automated target database search reported hits within a selected retention time window ($t_R \pm 0.25$ min), area counts and mass tolerance ($[M + H]^+ \pm 10$ mDa). The compounds detected with peak area values below the threshold are neglected. Final confirmation of the findings is accomplished by accurate mass analysis, using a 5 ppm mass accuracy threshold for final confirmation. Accurate mass analysis of characteristic fragment ions could also be used for providing unambiguous confirmation. Besides the use of abundant isotope signals (i.e., ^{37}Cl , ^{81}Br , ^{13}C , ^{34}S , ...), using, for instance, algorithms to evaluate isotopic signature profile matching/relative ion abundances (Sigma-Fit, i-Fit,...) could also be used for confirmation purposes.

LC-TOFMS Considerations. Table 1 lists the pesticides analyzed by the LC-TOFMS screening method. A fragmentor voltage of 190 V was selected as a compromise between sensitivity and fragmentation for confirmation purposes. Some of the compounds did not yield fragments even with higher voltages (i.e., 230 V), while in other cases, extensive fragmentation was obtained, which involved worse LODs when the protonated molecule was used (i.e., butoxycarboxin, oxamyl, aldicarb sulfone, dimethoate, cymoxanil, butocarboxin, aldicarb, bendiocarb, and methidathion). In these compounds, the use of more abundant fragment ions would provide better LODs. The limit of quantitation (LOQ) was determined in several fruit and vegetable matrixes including spiked food samples and solvent extracts for the studied compounds. As an example, the data obtained for the pepper matrix is shown in Table 1. The LOQ was equal to or less than 0.005 mg kg^{-1} for 43% of the compounds and less than or equal to 0.01 mg kg^{-1} for 60% of the compounds. Besides, the LOQ for 90% of the compounds was equal to or less than 0.05 mg kg^{-1} . Only three compounds were found to be less sensitive and the LOQ values were 0.1 mg kg^{-1} . Together with the nature of the compound, there are two points that has a strong effect on the sensitivity and limit of detection: the suppression of ionization and the presence in the matrix of interfering ions with nearly identical mass. The data shown in Table 1 were collected on a pepper spiked with the target analytes at different concentration levels. LOQs were calculated using $S/N = 10$ and a spiked pepper extract as the matrix.

From the data obtained in this study, the sensitivity and LOQs attained with the LC-TOFMS are fully satisfactory in most compounds, offering enough sensitivity to comply with MRLs established. In the scenario of fruits and vegetables (except the babyfood directive), the MRL for all combinations of pesticide/ matrix are of 0.05 mg kg^{-1} or higher. At this concentration level, LC-TOFMS provides appropriate sensitivity for 90% of the compounds. It should be noted that the remaining 10% of compounds included in the study do not ionize well and are not well suited to electrospray. Therefore, in the field of fruits and vegetables, the proposed approach is sensitive enough. From data on hand and experience on survey monitoring programs, LC-TOFMS offers robust and reliable performance for routine compounds, and we did not find examples of false positives (detected by LC-MS/MS but not by LC-TOFMS) in the range between 10 and 100 ng g^{-1} . Only at really low concentration levels (i.e., $0.1\text{-}5 \text{ ng g}^{-1}$) and depending on the individual compound, the performance of LC-TOFMS is not enough, compared with triple quadrupole instruments. It should be noted that the compounds which are not sensitive enough are basically due to poor ionization or simply by the fact that are more appropriate for GC analysis. In these cases, the results are usually unsatisfactory by either LC-TOFMS or LC-MS/MS.

On the other hand, the babyfood MRL is not difficult to achieve by LC-TOFMS.²³ The sensitivity provided by the

LC-TOFMS could be considered somehow a drawback but can be circumvented easily by several complementary strategies. Note that by using higher injected sample volumes, LODs could be lowered. The use of larger injected volumes increases the amount of analyte injected but also the chemical noise and matrix content. From our experience,²³ using 50 μL usually improved the results of the LOD by a factor of 2. Besides, using ultraperformance LC or a rapid resolution column operating at higher pressures, the S/N (and the LODs) can be improved by a factor of 2-5. In addition, we did not use the more advanced version of the instrument we operated. According to the manufacturer, the latest version of the instrument (Agilent 6210 TOF) provides a remarkable sensitivity increase with regards to the former version we used. Manufacturers are expected to make improvements to lower LODs by about a factor of 5-10 in the near future, which would almost even the sensitivity of current triple quadrupole instruments in the SRM mode. The combination of these points mentioned would increase the sensitivity of the LC-TOFMS so that it would not represent a problem in the proposed approach.

Unlike other approaches based solely on accurate mass measurements, the advantage of the proposed method is the use of t_R data. Sometimes, accurate mass data is not enough to confirm a compound. This is the case of some isobaric triazine herbicides with the same elemental composition and accurate mass but with different retention time (i.e., propazine and terbutylazine). Figure 2 shows the example of three isobaric compounds (acetamiprid, aldicarb sulfone, and butoxycarboxim). The accurate mass difference cannot be distinguished with the accuracy and mass resolution provided by TOF instruments. Isotopes could be used to distinguish acetamiprid, but the other two compounds have the same elemental composition. Therefore, retention time is a key parameter to construct the screening method. As long as the number of compounds is growing in the database, the chance of finding isobaric compounds (with the same elemental composition and/or accurate mass) is higher. These compounds should be identified by matching the retention time and elemental composition/isotope pattern matching. In this study, we did not find a case of the overlapping of two isobaric species. In that hypothetical case, fragment ions, adducts, and isotopic signatures could be used. However, it is unlikely to find a sample with positive results in two isobaric coeluting compounds.

Regarding the identification by retention time (t_R) matching in the screening method, the peak t_R precision was satisfactory with RSD values below 1% in most cases ($n = 7$). Only, it should be noted that the column equilibration should be carefully performed, particularly in the case of polar pesticides (i.e., with retention times < 12 min). Otherwise, it is possible to find false negatives due to t_R drifts (major t_R changes can occur in the case of polar pesticides), which hamper the identification of the compounds by the screening method, since this process is restricted to a limited t_R window ($t_R \pm 0.25$ min).

With the development of the screening method, another parameter to set together with the t_R is the accurate mass window for the automatic screening procedure. The use of narrower accurate mass extraction windows (i.e., < 40 mDa width) to enhance selectivity and signal-to noise ratio is described elsewhere.^{9,10}

In the proposed screening method, this factor enhances the overall performance since the number of false positives is dramatically reduced. In preliminary studies with 0.1-0.2 Da, the number of compounds detected (values greater than the established area threshold) was relatively high because it was easy to find compounds with the same nominal mass of the targets in a $t_R \pm 0.25$ min window. When narrowing the extracted mass window, the number of false positives was dramatically reduced. Only some compounds give false positives due to the presence of large concentrations of compounds with similar mass (i.e., cambendazole), and peaks appeared in the XIC, despite that the selected mass range was not overlapped with the mass of the interference. These kind of false positives are easily detected and removed in the subsequent confirmation step by LC-TOFMS accurate mass analysis. A mass window of $[M + H]^+ \pm 10$ mDa was found to yield high selectivity, and the number of false positives were typically below 5% of the studied compounds.

The performance of accurate mass measurements by LC- TOFMS in fruit and vegetables samples has been

studied in detail and is described elsewhere.^{9,10} In this study, we also perform accurate mass analysis of the 100 pesticides studied in vegetables samples. As shown in Table 1, the accuracy was excellent with errors below 2 ppm in most cases, an average error of 1 ppm. In addition, no significant differences were observed when comparing the accuracy obtained in solvent and matrix-matched standards and also by the concentration level as shown in Figure 3. However, we observed that the mass accuracy decreases with higher concentration ($>0.5 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$), depending on the sensitivity of the compound at a defined concentration level (i.e., azoxystrobin, thiabendazole, and carbendazim).

Linearity was also evaluated, and LC-TOFMS offer 2-3 orders of magnitude with regression coefficients (R^2) > 0.99 in most cases. As an example, Figure 4 shows the calibration curves of imazalil and prochloraz, two postharvest fungicides. Both compounds yield excellent coefficient regression with over three decades of concentration (imazalil, $0.0001\text{-}0.25 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$; prochloraz, $0.001\text{-}2 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$). However, in the case of imazalil, linearity is $0.0001\text{-}0.25 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ and concentration levels above 0.5 mg kg^{-1} are outside the linear dynamic range, which might give rise to quantitation errors, particularly for this compound, because it is usually present at large concentration in fruits samples (i.e., MRLs in citrus are in the $5\text{-}10 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ range). This drawback in quantitative terms is solved by performing the final quantitation with LC-MS/MS.

TOFMS instruments offer unsurpassed performance for screening purposes, can also effectively provide concentration values, and are accurate enough to differentiate between positive and negative samples or pesticide concentrations below or above the MRL. However, for a dedicated quantitation method, LC-MS/MS gives more reliable results. In addition, with triple quadrupole instruments operating in the selected reaction monitoring mode, confirmation can be accomplished at low concentration levels with two SRM transitions. LC-TOFMS offers unambiguous identification due to accurate mass analysis with routine sub-2 ppm accuracy. In contrast, there are several compounds (i.e., thiabendazole, imazalil, ...) with low in-source CID fragmentation, which are unable to give rise to fragment ions for confirmation purposes. These two issues (quantitation over a large concentration range and confirmation criteria) make the use of LC-MS/MS advisable. In addition, the use of LC-MS/MS (or other reanalysis) for confirmation is needed to meet "confirmation" by definition in which a second result confirms the first, according to Quality Control Pesticide Residue Guidelines.⁶

Application of the Automated Screening Method to Samples Spiked with a Selected Group of Pesticides. To evaluate the performance of the proposed screening method, different fruit and vegetable samples were fortified with a selected group of pesticides at different concentration levels. As examples, the results of two of the samples studied are shown in Tables 3 and 4.

The studied lemon extract was fortified with 0.05 mg kg^{-1} of 25 known pesticides (from the list of 100 included in the method). The data file of the screening method was inserted in the software, and the sample yielded 28 positives, 100% of the spiked compounds, and 3 false positives. Confirmation was assessed with accurate mass analysis below 5 ppm for the 25 compounds (see Table 3). Except for the less sensitive compounds (i.e., flufenoxuron and teflubenzuron), with concentration values close to the LOQ, accuracy was below 3 ppm error, which provided the unambiguous identification of the fortified pesticides. In contrast, cambendazole, difenoxuron, and fluometuron were identified by the automated screening method but rejected in the LC-TOFMS identification step by accurate mass analysis. Only 3% were false positive. No false negatives were detected.

Table 4 shows the case of a lemon extract fortified at the 0.125 mg kg^{-1} level, with 15 spiked (known) compounds. Twenty pesticides (of 100) were detected: no false negatives and 5 false positives which were neglected in the identification step by LC-TOFMS accurate mass analysis. A total of 15 compounds were successfully identified. This evidence shows the usefulness of this automated screening procedure for the control

of large lists of target compounds. The time required to perform the screening was 3-5 min, using a laptop, which is less than the re-equilibration time of the HPLC column. Therefore, it does not represent a bottleneck in the whole screening procedure. Only the detected compounds (upper limit of the area threshold) should be checked and confirmed manually (extracting ions and checking accuracy) or automatically, since reports can be generated with the accuracy according to the expected theoretical m/z value for each compound.

Together with the target screening capabilities, LC-TOFMS offers the possibility of performing a posteriori nontarget or unknown analysis.¹⁴⁻¹⁷ In fact, a “fingerprint” of the vegetable samples (full-scan LC-TOFMS analysis, including any analyte covered by the sample treatment and ionization conditions) is recorded and can be used “a posteriori” for the identification and quantitation of unexpected, unknown, or banned compounds which were not monitored when the analysis was performed. This is a unique feature of LC-TOFMS, which makes it very attractive for comprehensive pesticide residue analysis. An example concerning “a posteriori” reanalysis of a banned pesticide (isofenphos-methyl in pepper) is shown in detail.

This comprehensive screening step of target, nontarget, and unknown pesticides is followed by a final confirmation and quantitation step by LC-MS/MS using the SRM mode, instruments with high duty cycle, triple quadrupole or hybrid linear ion trap triple quadrupole (QTRAP) instruments, which offer the possibility of performing quantitative analysis of a large list of target compounds (i.e., 100-150) with two SRM transitions.

Liquid Chromatography-Tandem Mass Spectrometry Method. The proposed approach is based on the combination of a screening step by LC-TOFMS followed by dedicated quantitation and confirmation by LC-MS/MS in the SRM mode. Thus, in parallel with the LC-TOFMS screening method as a model, an LC-MS/MS method was developed for 81 pesticides, the most commonly used of those analyzed by LC-TOFMS. A hybrid triple quadrupole linear ion trap (QTRAP) analyzer working in the SRM mode was used. Normally, the proposed LC-MS/MS method would be based on the selected list of priority pesticides, updated annually by different organizations, including the most commonly detected or used compounds. Up to 200 compounds can be analyzed in a unique LC-MS/MS run, with 2 MRM transitions. This method was used to provide further confirmation of the positive results and reliable quantitative data. The MRM transitions and conditions of operation in the MRM mode are shown in Table 2.

The main analytical features of the method, including LODs, LOQs, and linearity, are shown in Table 5. A pepper extract was used as a model in matrix matched standards to obtain the calibration curves and to calculate LODs and LOQs. In terms of sensitivity, the LOD for approximately 80% of the compounds was equal to or less than 0.001 mg kg⁻¹, and only for 3.7% of them, the LOD was equal to 0.01 mg kg⁻¹. For the compounds with a LOD within 0.005 and 0.01 mg kg⁻¹ (11%), sensitivity could be improved using alternative LC conditions. It is, sometimes, a limitation in the development of a multiresidue method for the determination of trace compounds. In terms of quantitation by matrix-matched calibration, a linear dynamic range was obtained with a range between the LODs to 0.5 mg kg⁻¹ with correlation coefficients > 0.9970.

As long as new pesticides are being detected or used, this list of common target compounds analyzed by LC-MS/MS can be updated, while the capabilities of LC-TOFMS to include new target compounds in the screening step are theoretically unlimited. This is the main drawback of LC-MS/MS methods, the limited number of compounds analyzed in a unique run. Therefore, the combination of both techniques provides unsurpassed performance for a wide range of compounds.

The hybrid triple quadrupole linear ion trap (QqLIT) instrument (“QTRAP”) we used to perform the LC-MS/MS analyses combined the SRM mode with attractive working modes (enhanced product ion (EPI) and MS³ modes) for the unambiguous confirmation of pesticides with poor fragmentation at low concentration levels, which cannot be easily confirmed by triple quadrupole instruments due to the high MRM ratio (or absence of

transitions) between the two transitions for confirmatory purposes. The MRM ratio is typically used as a key parameter for confirmation purposes, particularly when coeluting analytes or matrix interferences are present in multiresidue analysis. A limitation of the use of the MRM ratio is at low concentrations of analyte, the second MRM transition is not detected due to a higher difference between both MRM transitions. This is the case of the pesticide spinosyn A, with a MRM ratio of 25. A possible alternative is the use of information-dependent acquisition (IDA) experiments to trigger additional survey scans, so that it is plausible to combine a survey scan acquired in the MRM operation mode (triple quadrupole) with another survey scan in the EPI mode or in the MS³ mode (using the instrument as a linear ion trap) in one single run. Thus, one MRM transition can be used for quantification, and the structural information obtained with MS² by using the EPI mode or with the MS³ scan mode can be successful for the confirmation of analytes.

As an example, the data obtained from the IDA experiments performed on spinosyn A are shown in Figure 5. The spectra obtained in the EPI mode for spinosyn A shows two fragment ions (m/z 142 and 98) as a result of the fragmentation of the precursor ion m/z 732. However, the intensity of the fragment ion m/z 98 is approximately 10%. With an additional survey scan of MS³ for spinosyn A, further structural information is obtained, since the fragment ion m/z 142 provided another abundant fragment ion at m/z 98.0. Therefore, in this example, the use of this instrument enables one to unequivocally confirm the finding using a MS³ step. In addition, the use of the EPI mode does not involve a remarkable sensitivity decrease, while the identification confirmation capabilities are better than a conventional triple quadrupole instrument. With this approach, the number of compounds to be analyzed could be duplicated when a MRM survey scan is combined with an EPI scan in a MS run. For instance, approximately 240 MRM transitions could be acquired as quantifier mass transitions, and simultaneously the EPI mode could be used for confirmatory purposes.

Application to Real Samples. The proposed approach was applied to different samples from a monitoring program performed in cooperation with the Andalusian Food Safety Authority. The proposed approach was evaluated for ~40 different crops samples. As an example, the results obtained in three selected samples are shown in Table 6. Each sample yielded various positives (Apple No. 22080, carbendazim, imazalil, thiacloprid, thiabendazole, malathion, ethoxyquin, and imazalil metabolite; Pear No. 22078, imazalil, thiabendazole, tebuconazole, ethoxyquin, imazalil metabolite, and carbendazim; Grapes No. 2733, azoxystrobin, carbendazim, and thiabendazole). False positives: lenacil, thiofanox sulfone (22080); albendazole and aldicarb sulfone (22078); and cambendazole and oxfendazole (2733). As shown in Table 6, the rate of false positives is below 3% of the screened compounds. The results show the potential of the proposed approach. From previous experience on a surveillance regional program, from over 300 samples studied, 54% of the samples were found free of any pesticide. Only 46% contained at least 1 pesticide, which means that the LC- MS/MS step for over 50% of the samples could have been saved. This feature is plausible due to the excellent full-scan sensitivity of state-of-the-art LC-TOFMS instruments, approaching unsurpassed LC-MS/MS's LODs. In addition, nontarget and unknown analysis and "a posteriori" re-examination of samples by LC- TOFMS is feasible. An example is the case of the EU food safety alert, due to the presence of a nonauthorized insecticide (isofenphos-methyl) in selected pepper samples from the south of Spain. Since this compound is not authorized, it was not included in routine LC-MS/MS methods, and the information of its presence and concentration is not recorded, obviously since it is not expected. However, the use of LC-TOFMS enables the re-examination of former pepper samples, to check whether the banned compound was used before the alert. As an example, the chromatogram of a positive finding is shown in Figure 6. Isofenphos-methyl was unequivocally identified by means of LC-TOFMS, thus complementing the features of the LC-MS/MS method.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this work, a new approach based on LC-TOFMS and LC-MS/MS analysis has been proposed for the comprehensive screening of target pesticides. The proposed approach consists of three steps. First, samples are analyzed by LC-TOFMS and the proposed method provides the screening and preliminary identification of the species by retention time and m/z mass window, followed by subsequent identification (if positive results) by LC-TOFMS accurate mass analysis (second step). Final confirmation and reliable quantitation is accomplished in the final step by LC-MS/MS analysis with two MRM transitions. This scenario proposed for target pesticides is complemented with the ability of LC-TOFMS for the analyses of both nontarget and unknown pesticides and the possibility of recording a data file as a history of each individual sample. The identification criteria, quantitation capabilities, and effectiveness of the proposed comprehensive screening method have been evaluated with various spiked food extracts and also in real samples obtaining satisfactory results. Steps are being taken in order to increase the throughput of these screening methods, by means of using LC columns with small particle size (i.e., rapid/fast resolution) to reduce the total analysis time per run (below 15 min), and also the potential of the proposed approach is being tested with a large number of pesticides (i.e., 400).

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Figure 1. Proposed workflow for the screening, identification, confirmation, and quantitation of target pesticides in vegetable samples. The approach consists of three steps: (1) screening by LC- TOFMS with retention time/accurate mass m/z windows; (2) identification via accurate mass measurements (<5 ppm error); and (3) confirmation (2 MRM transitions) and quantitation by LC-MS/MS.

Figure 2. The importance of retention time information: accurate mass spectrum of three isobaric pesticides, acetamiprid, aldicarb sulfone, and butoxycarboxim. Acetamiprid can be distinguished due to its isotopic signature corresponding to one chlorine atom. For the two remaining, the use of retention time is mandatory, since they have the same elemental composition and accurate mass.

Figure 3. Ruggedness of accurate mass measurements performed on vegetable extracts at different concentration levels. The accuracy is unaffected by different concentration levels (0.01-0.5 mg kg⁻¹) and also by the matrix.

Figure 4. Calibration curves obtained for prochloraz and imazalil by LC-TOFMS analysis. Despite that imazalil has linearity over 3 orders of magnitude, quantitation above 0.5 mg kg⁻¹ is not reliable enough.

Figure 5. Application of LC-MS/MS for the confirmation of spinosyn A, a pesticide with low CID fragmentation in a triple quadrupole, using a hybrid triple quadrupole linear ion trap instrument: (a) total ion chromatogram; (b) enhanced product ion (EPI) scan mode; and (c) MS³ mode. The combination of survey scans using the MRM, EPI, and MS³ modes by means of information-dependent acquisition (IDA) experiments is very useful for confirmatory purposes.

Figure 6. (a) Total ion chromatogram corresponding to the LC-TOFMS analysis of a pepper extract. Retrospective examination and analysis of this sample revealed the presence of banned isofenphos-methyl (0.071 mg kg^{-1}) at 27.8 min; (b) extracted ion chromatogram of the detected species used for quantitation purposes (m/z 230.98 ± 0.01 Da); and (c) accurate mass spectrum of isofenphos-methyl in the studied sample.

Table 1. Accurate Mass Measurements, Retention Times (t_R), and Limits of Quantitation (LOQ) of the Studied 100 Pesticides in Food Extracts Prepared by QuEChERS^a

pesticide	selected ion ([M + H] ⁺)	m/z_{exptl}	m/z_{calcd}	error (ppm)	t_R (min)	RSD (%) t_R (n) 7)	LOQ ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)
cyromazine	C ₆ H ₁₁ N ₆	167.1038	167.10397	1.0	3.59	0.45	10
butoxicarboxin ^b	C ₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄ S	223.0747	223.07470	0.02	3.88	0.44	80
carbendazim	C ₉ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₂	192.0768	192.07675	0.2	6.97	0.29	10
thiabendazole	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₃ OCl	202.0431	202.04334	1.2	8.56	0.42	10
oxamyl ^{b,c}	C ₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃ SNa	242.0563	242.05698	2.8	11.18	0.31	50
aldicarb sulfone ^b	C ₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄ S	223.0747	223.0747	0.02	11.35	0.25	100
nitenpyram	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	271.0961	271.09563	1.7	12.08	0.34	40
methomyl ^{b,c}	C ₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ SNa	185.0358	185.03552	1.5	12.16	0.32	30
chloridazon	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₃ OCl	222.0454	222.04286	1.6	14.70	0.15	4
ethiofencarb sulfoxide	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ NO ₃ S	242.0849	242.08454	1.5	13.57	0.24	30
thiofanox sulfoxide	C ₉ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₃ S	235.1111	235.11109	0.1	13.71	0.17	30
thiamethoxam	C ₈ H ₁₁ N ₅ O ₃ ClS	292.0263	292.02656	0.5	13.72	0.21	6
methiocarb sulfoxide	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ NO ₃ S	242.0844	242.08454	0.6	14.45	0.24	30
metamitron	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ O	203.0930	203.09273	1.3	14.55	0.28	2
imazalil-Met	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ OCl ₂	257.0245	257.02429	0.8	14.58	0.17	3
cambendazole	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S	303.0911	303.09102	0.2	14.88	0.14	3
ethiofencarb sulfone	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ NO ₄ S	258.0794	258.07945	0.2	15.12	0.19	40
imidacloprid	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₅ O ₂ Cl	256.0596	256.05957	0.1	15.50	0.28	15
oxfendazole	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₃ S	316.0756	316.07503	1.8	15.54	0.06	1.5
dimethoate ^b	C ₅ H ₁₂ NO ₃ PS ₂	230.0067	230.0069	0.9	16.10	0.32	30
acetamiprid	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ N ₄ Cl	223.0742	223.0745	1.3	16.31	0.11	10
thiofanox sulfone	C ₉ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄ S	251.1063	251.10600	1.2	16.38	0.13	40
prochloraz-Met	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ NOCl ₃	282.0217	282.02137	1.6	16.78	0.07	5
cymoxanil ^b	C ₇ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₃	199.0828	199.08256	1.0	17.45	0.15	100
albendazole	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₂ S	266.0962	266.09577	1.6	17.86	0.09	1.6
butocarboxin ^c	C ₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ SNa	213.0667	213.06682	0.6	17.1/17.6	0.14	15
methiocarb sulfone	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ NO ₄ S	258.0791	258.07945	1.3	17.31	0.10	50
thiacloprid	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ ClS	253.0307	253.03092	0.9	17.78	0.14	10
imazalil	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₂ OCl ₂	297.0556	297.0559	0.1	17.90	0.10	1.5
mebendazole	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₃	296.1029	296.10296	0.2	18.04	0.10	1.5
aldicarb ^b	C ₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S	191.0847	191.08487	0.9	18.35	0.10	80
oxadixyl	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄	279.1340	279.13393	0.2	18.72	0.17	6
simazine	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₃ OCl	202.0852	202.08539	1.0	18.72	0.06	4
fluroxypyr	C ₇ H ₆ N ₂ O ₃ FCl ₂	254.9739	254.9734	1.9	18.78	0.11	50
monuron	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₂ OCl	199.0629	199.06306	0.8	18.79	0.08	3
flubendazole	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃ F	314.0931	314.09354	1.4	18.80	0.065	5
lenacil	C ₁₃ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂	235.1443	235.1441	0.8	19.20	0.10	30
methylthiophanate	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂	343.0527	343.05292	0.6	19.45	0.14	15
pyrimethanil	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₃	200.1180	200.11822	1.2	19.64	0.09	0.6
spiroxamine	C ₁₈ H ₃₆ NO ₂	298.2740	298.27405	0.2	19.75	0.1	0.6
ethoxyquin	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ NO	218.1536	218.15394	1.5	19.88	0.27	2
prometryn	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ N ₅ S	242.1428	242.14339	2.4	20.09	0.10	0.2
fenbendazole	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂ S	300.0798	300.08012	1.1	20.19	0.05	1
carbofuran	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ NO ₃	222.1120	222.11246	2.1	20.40	0.10	20
chlorotoluron	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ OCl	213.0795	213.07891	2.7	20.40	0.10	4
bendiocarb ^b	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ NO ₄	224.0914	224.09173	1.5	20.58	0.10	70
spinosyn A	C ₄₁ H ₆₆ NO ₁₀	732.4684	732.46812	0.4	20.86	0.10	2
fluometuron	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ OF ₃	233.0897	233.08962	0.3	20.95	0.048	3
atrazine	C ₈ H ₁₅ N ₅ Cl	216.1010	216.10104	0.2	21.07	0.08	1.6
miconazole	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₂ OCl ₄	414.9934	414.9933	0.2	21.08	0.11	6
thiofanox ^c	C ₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ NaS	241.0981	241.09812	0.1	21.10	0.09	20
metalaxyl	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ NO ₄	280.1541	280.15433	0.8	21.12	0.02	2
isoproturon	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₂ O	207.1492	207.14918	0.1	21.19	0.04	0.4
diazoxon	C ₁₂ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₄ P	289.1313	289.13117	0.4	21.20	0.18	10
difenoxuron	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₃	287.1397	287.13901	2.3	21.21	0.042	2
diuron	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₂ OCl ₂	233.0246	233.02429	1.3	21.28	0.14	5
monolinuron	C ₉ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	215.0580	215.05818	0.8	21.51	0.07	10
ethiofencarb	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ NO ₂ S	226.0895	226.08944	0.25	21.60	0.13	30
spinosyn D	C ₄₂ H ₆₈ NO ₁₀	746.4828	746.48377	1.3	21.64	0.12	2
metobromuron	C ₉ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ Br	259.0073	259.00766	1.4	22.02	0.09	15
dimethomorph	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ NO ₄ Cl	388.1309	388.13101	0.3	22.1/22.5	0.12	10
flazasulfuron	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₅ F ₃ S	408.0581	408.0584	0.7	22.31	0.08	2
ioxynil	C ₇ H ₄ NO ₂	371.8368	371.83769	2.4	22.55	0.072	70
triadimenol	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂ Cl	296.1157	296.11603	1.1	22.7/23.1	0.10	10
prochloraz	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ Cl ₃	376.0388	376.03808	0.1	22.71	0.09	3
propazine	C ₉ H ₁₇ N ₅ Cl	230.1168	230.11669	0.4	22.98	0.03	0.4
cyproconazole	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₃ OCl	292.1209	292.12111	0.7	23.32	0.12	2
methiocarb	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ NO ₂ S	226.0898	226.08962	0.8	23.40	0.08	80
terbuthylazine	C ₉ H ₁₇ N ₅ Cl	230.1169	230.11669	0.9	23.42	0.08	3
chloroxuron	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	291.0892	291.08948	1.0	23.50	0.11	4
bromuconazole	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₃ OBrCl ₂	375.9611	375.96135	0.7	23.6/24.5	0.12	10

linuron	C ₉ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂	249.0190	249.0192	0.8	23.70	0.12	10
methidathion ^{b,c}	NaC ₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄ PS ₃	324.9511	324.95108	0.05	23.71	0.12	50
fenamiphos	C ₁₃ H ₂₃ NO ₃ PS	304.1134	304.11308	1.1	23.78	0.02	10
chlorbromuron	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ BrCl	292.9692	292.96869	1.7	24.02	0.08	20
azoxystrobin	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅	404.1241	404.12409	0.1	24.08	0.11	2
promecarb	C ₁₂ H ₁₈ NO ₂	208.1337	208.1332	2.4	24.08	0.05	5
tebuconazole	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ N ₃ OCl	308.1530	308.15241	1.9	24.50	0.1	10
triadimefon	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ Cl	294.1005	294.10038	0.4	24.52	0.1	4
tetraconazole	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₃ OF ₄ Cl ₂	372.0291	372.0288	0.8	24.61	0.08	3
diflubenzuron	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ ClF ₂	311.0395	311.03933	0.5	24.91	0.11	50
iprodione	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₃ Cl ₂	330.0406	330.04067	0.2	25.30	0.10	60
triflumizol	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₃ OF ₃ Cl	346.0929	346.09285	0.1	25.57	0.08	3
malathion	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ O ₆ PS ₂	331.0439	331.04334	1.7	25.60	0.08	8
procymidone	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ NO ₂ Cl ₂	284.0243	284.02396	1.2	25.61	0.05	15
neburon	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ OCl ₂	275.0710	275.07124	0.9	25.83	0.09	3
vinclozolin	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ NO ₃ Cl ₂	286.0034	286.00322	0.6	26.35	0.08	80
mecarbam	C ₁₀ H ₂₁ NO ₅ PS ₂	330.0593	330.05933	0.1	26.36	0.11	3
triflumuron	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₃ F ₃ Cl	359.0404	359.04048	0.2	26.40	0.07	40
dichlofluanid	C ₉ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂ F ₂ S ₂	332.9701	332.96958	1.6	26.61	0.13	100
hexaflumuron	C ₁₆ H ₉ N ₂ O ₃ F ₆ Cl ₂	460.9889	460.98889	0.01	27.20	0.08	30
buprofezin	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ N ₃ OS	306.1639	306.16346	1.4	27.21	0.07	3
diazinon	C ₁₂ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₃ PS	305.1089	305.10832	1.2	27.50	0.05	1
teflubenzuron	C ₁₄ H ₇ N ₂ O ₂ F ₄ Cl ₂	380.9818	380.98152	0.7	27.56	0.1	40
thiobencarb	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ NOClS	258.0712	258.07139	0.7	27.57	0.06	1
lufenuron	C ₁₇ H ₈ N ₂ O ₃ F ₈ Cl ₂	510.9857	510.98570	0.0	28.61	0.09	25
pyriproxyfen	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ NO ₃	322.1441	322.14377	1.0	29.17	0.08	0.5
flufenoxuron	C ₂₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃ F ₆ Cl	489.0434	489.04351	0.2	29.22	0.08	20
chlorfluazuron	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₃ F ₅ Cl ₃	539.9700	539.97024	0.45	29.70	0.07	20
hexythiazox	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ ClS	353.1093	353.1085	2.2	30.00	0.07	50

^a The accurate mass analysis data was performed on a pepper extract spiked at the 0.1 mg kg⁻¹ level of the studied pesticides. Limits of quantitation (LOQ) were estimated by using S/N ratio of 10:1 and confirmed by using experimental data from a spiked pepper extract fortified at different concentration levels from 0.0001 to 0.5 mg kg⁻¹. ^b Sodium adduct formation. ^c Extensive fragmentation of the protonated molecule. The sensitivity and LOQ could be improved by using a fragment ion instead of the [M + H]⁺.

Table 2. LC-MS/MS Method: MRM Transitions and Values of MS Parameters Optimized for MRM Operation Mode Using a Hybrid Triple Quadrupole Linear Ion Trap System (QTRAP)

pesticide	t _R (min)	MRM1	MRM2	dwelt time (ms)	DP	EP	CEP	CE (MRM1, MRM2)	CXP (MRM1, MRM2)
cyromazine	6.2	167.0/85.1	167.0/108. 1	5	37	5	14.90	(24, 28)	(2, 2)
butoxycarboxin	9.7	223.1/106.2	223.1/63.0	8	35	6	16.47	(10, 16)	(1, 1)
carbendazim	8.8	192.4/160.2	192.4/132. 1	5	52	5	15.61	(24, 42)	(3, 2)
thiabendazole	8.8	202.0/131.2	202.0/175. 2	8	59	5	15.88	(35, 42)	(2, 2)
oxamyl	9.7	220.1/72.2	220.1/90.1	8	37	6	16.39	(11, 21)	(1, 1)
aldicarb sulfone	10.2	223.2/148.1	223.2/86.0	5	45	4	16.48	(12, 20)	(3, 2)
nitenpyram	8.8	271.2/99.1	271.2/225. 1	5	51	4	17.82	(14, 20)	(3, 1)
methomyl	11.5	163.3/106.1	163.3/88.1	5	20	5	14.80	(14, 14)	(1.8, 1.8)
chloridazon	15.0	222.0/92.0	222.0/77.0	5	60	3	16.44	(47, 38)	(1, 1)
thiametoxam	11.5	292.2/211.2	292.2/132. 1	5	41	3	18.41	(18, 24)	(3, 2)
methiocarb sulfoxide	11.2	242.2/185.2	242.2/170. 2	5	42	5	17.01	(16, 32)	(3, 3)
metamitron	13.8	203.1/175.3	203.1/104. 1	5	42	4	15.91	(27, 23)	(1, 2)
cambendazole	9.8	303.1/217.3	303.1/261. 2	5	66	7	18.71	(38, 22)	(3, 4)
imidacloprid	15.3	256.3/209.2	256.3/175. 1	5	56	5	17.40	(24, 26)	(2.5, 2)
oxfendazole	12.5	316.2/159.1	316.2/191. 1	5	63	4	19.08	(41, 26)	(2, 2)
dimethoate	16.3	230.1/199.2	230.1/125. 1	5	38	2.6	16.67	(27, 14)	(2.2, 2.9)
acetamiprid	16.01	223.2/126.2	223.2/56.1	5	50	5	16.48	(27.5, 31)	(2, 2)
cymoxanil	18.1	199.1/128.2	199.1/111. 0	8	32	4	15.80	(12, 23)	(3, 2)
albendazole	17.3	266.2/234.1	266.2/191. 2	5	64	6	17.68	(26, 46)	(2, 4)
butocarboxin	18.4	213.2/75.0	213.2/156. 0	5	77	6	16.20	(18, 12)	(1, 3)
methiocarb sulfone	17.6	258.2/122.1	258.2/201. 1	10	44	5	17.46	(24, 11)	(2, 3)
thiacloprid	18.2	253.2/126.1	253.2/99.0	5	52	5	17.32	(27.5, 56)	(2, 2)
imazalil	16.8	297.1/159.1	297.1/109. 2	5	20	5	18.55	(28, 26)	(2, 2.5)
mebendazole	17.9	296.2/264.3	296.2/105. 3	5	52	8	18.52	(26, 45)	(3, 2)
aldicarb	19.2	213.2/89.1	213.2/116. 2	5	30	5	16.20	(22, 15.8)	(2, 2)
oxadixyl	19.2	279.2/219.2	279.2/102. 1	8	54	4	18.04	(13, 12)	(2, 2)
simazine	19.9	202.1/132.2	202.1/124. 2	5	50	5	15.89	(23, 25)	(1.7, 1.79)
fluroxypyr	33.3	255.0/237.2	255.0/209. 0	10	40	3	17.37	(13, 24)	(4, 2)
monuron	19.6	199.2/72.2	199.2/126. 1	5	26	5	15.80	(32, 34)	(2, 2)
lenacil	19.8	235.2/153.3	235.2/136. 3	5	33	5	16.81	(25, 43)	(2, 2)
pyrimethanil	21.9	200.3/67.0	200.3/77.1	5	45	5	15.84	(55, 58)	(1, 1)
spiroxamine	18.8	298.0/144.3	298.0/100. 0	5	43	8	18.57	(29, 43)	(2, 1)
ethoxyquin	21.5	218.3/174.3	218.3/160. 3	5	69	7	16.34	(40, 44)	(2, 2)
prometryn	21.29	242.3/158.2	242.3/200. 2	5	18	5	17.01	(22, 33)	(3, 3)
fenbendazole	20.5	300.0/268.2	300.0/159. 3	5	55	4	18.63	(25, 46)	(2, 2)
carbofuran	21.6	222.3/165.3	222.3/123. 2	5	40	5	16.45	(16, 20)	(2, 2)
chlorotoluron	21.6	213.2/72.0	213.2/140. 1	5	54	5	16.20	(39, 32)	(1, 2)
bendiocarb	21.7	224.2/109.1	224.2/167. 3	5	31	5	16.48	(10, 26)	(1, 4)
spinosyn A	19.5	732.7/142.2	732.7/189. 3	5	20	5	30.74	(40, 42)	(2, 2)
fluometuron	22.06	233.2/72.1	233.2/160. 2	5	41	5	16.76	(34, 35)	(2, 2)
atrazine	22.3	216.1/174.1	216.1/104. 1	5	47	4	16.28	(20, 40)	(2.5, 2)
miconazole	20.0	415.1/159.1	415.1/227. 2	5	40	6	21.85	(40, 26)	(2, 2)
metalaxyl	22.3	280.2/220.2	280.2/192. 3	5	50	4	18.04	(21, 22)	(2, 3)
isoproturon	22.3	207.2/72.1	207.2/165.	5	56	7	16.03	(33, 18)	(2, 7)

difenoxuron	22.0	287.1/123.2	287.1/72.1	5	48	5	18.27	(35, 23)	(1, 2)
diuron	22.5	233.1/72.1	233.1/160.2	5	41	5	16.76	(34, 35)	(2, 2)
monolinuron	22.9	215.1/148.3	215.1/126.1	5	40	5	16.25	(18, 22)	(2, 2)
ethiofencarb	22.8	226.2/107.1	226.2/164.2	5	28	5	16.56	(21, 8)	(1.8, 2)
spinosyn D	20.2	746.5/142.2	746.5/189.2	8	20	5	31.13	(46, 40)	(2, 2)
metobromuron	23.5	259.0/170.1	259.0/148.2	5	39	5	17.48	(26, 21)	(3, 3)
dimethomorph	23.5	388.2/301.2	388.2/165.2	5	65	5	21.01	(28, 40)	(2.7, 2.3)
flazasulfuron	23.2	408.0/182.3	408.0/226.8	5	32	5	21.65	(30, 30)	(3, 4)
prochloraz	24.0	376.1/308.1	376.1/266.1	5	40	5	20.76	(16, 21)	(3.2, 3)
propazine	24.7	230.2/188.2	230.2/146.2	5	48	5	16.67	(31, 21)	(2, 3)
cyproconazole	24.7	292.2/70.1	292.2/125.1	5	63	5	18.41	(49, 43)	(1, 2)
methiocarb	24.9	226.2/121.2	226.2/169.2	5	20	5	16.56	(24, 13)	(2, 2)
terbuthylazine	25.2	230.2/174.3	230.2/146.1	5	48	5	16.67	(23, 31)	(3, 2)
chloroxuron	24.7	291.0/72.1	291.0/218.1	5	62	5	18.38	(40, 34)	(3, 2)
bromuconazole	25.1	376.0/159.2	376.0/70.0	5	47	5	20.76	(28, 44)	(2, 1)
linuron	25.4	249.1/160.0	249.1/182.2	5	50	5	17.20	(22, 19)	(3, 3)
methidathion	25.3	302.9/145.2	302.9/84.9	5	20	5	18.71	(13, 22)	(1.3, 1.8)
fenamiphos	25.1	304.2/217.2	304.2/234.2	5	63	5	18.74	(26, 20)	(2, 3)
chlorbromuron	25.9	293.1/204.1	293.1/182.2	5	48	5	18.43	(24, 20)	(3, 3)
azoxystrobin	25.1	404.0/372.0	404.0/344.0	5	40	5	21.54	(20, 33)	(3, 3)
promecarb	25.68	208.1/109.2	208.1/151.3	5	32	5	16.05	(20, 14)	(3, 3)
tebuconazole	26.1	308.2/70.0	308.2/125.2	5	48	4	18.86	(40, 49)	(1, 2)
diflubenzuron	26.3	311.1/141.0	311.1/158.2	5	40	5	18.94	(40, 20)	(1.5, 1.8)
iprodione	29.0	330.0/245.0	330.0/101.0	5	50	5	19.47	(15, 32)	(4, 2)
triflumizol	27.8	346.2/278.2	346.2/73.1	5	30	5	19.92	(12, 22)	(3, 2)
malathion	27.1	331.0/127.2	331.0/285.2	5	43	5	19.50	(16, 12)	(2, 3)
neburon	27.6	275.2/57.2	275.2/88.3	5	74	5	17.93	(34, 22)	(2, 2)
vinclozolin	27.7	286.1/214.0	286.1/179.0	8	40	7	18.24	(17, 27)	(2, 2)
triflumuron	27.7	359.1/156.1	359.1/139.1	5	43	8	20.28	(23, 46)	(2, 3)
dichlofluanid	28.2	333.2/123.1	333.2/224.2	10	38	5	19.56	(28, 15)	(2, 2)
hexaflumuron	28.2	461.1/158.1	461.1/141.3	5	50	5	23.14	(25.7, 50)	(2, 2)
buprofezin	30.7	306.4/201.2	306.4/116.2	5	20	5	18.81	(15, 22)	(2.5, 2)
diazinon	29.7	305.3/169.3	305.3/153.0	5	41	5	18.77	(26, 27)	(3, 2.4)
teflubenzuron	29.1	381.3/141.0	381.3/158.2	10	51	5	20.90	(50, 22)	(2, 3)
lufenuron	29.6	511.1/158.1	511.1/141.2	5	65	5	24.54	(25, 50)	(2.8, 2)
pyriproxyfen	30.8	322.3/96.2	322.3/227.3	5	39	5	19.25	(23, 16)	(4, 3)
flufenoxuron	30.2	489.1/158.1	489.1/141.1	5	50	5	23.92	(24, 28)	(2.5, 2.5)

Table 3. Screening and Identification by LC-TOFMS of 25 Target Compounds in a Spiked Lemon Extract Fortified at 0.05 mg kg⁻¹ Level^a

pesticide	<i>m/z</i> _{exptl}	<i>m/z</i> _{theoretical}	(ppm)	confirmation
acetamiprid	223.0744	223.0745	0.5	yes
atrazine	216.1006	216.1014	2.0	yes
azoxystrobin	404.1243	404.12409	0.5	yes
buprofezin	306.1635	306.16346	0.1	yes
carbendazim	192.0764	192.07675	1.8	yes
dimethoate	230.0070	230.0069	0.4	yes
dimethomorph	388.1313	388.13101	0.7	yes
diuron	233.0240	233.02429	1.3	yes
flufenoxuron	489.0414	489.04351	4.3	yes
imazalil	297.0557	297.05559	0.4	yes
imidacloprid	256.0593	256.05957	1.1	yes
lufenuron	510.9861	510.98570	2.4	yes
met-thiophanate	343.0524	343.05292	0.8	yes
piriproxifen	322.1442	322.14377	1.3	yes
prochloraz	376.0376	376.03808	1.3	yes
simazine	202.0850	202.08539	2.0	yes
spinosyn A	732.4682	732.46812	0.1	yes
spinosyn D	746.4844	746.48377	0.8	yes
teflubenzuron	380.9828	380.98152	3.3	yes
terbuthylazine	230.1168	230.11669	0.4	yes
thiabendazole	202.0433	202.04334	0.2	yes
triflumizol	346.0932	346.09285	1.0	yes

“Unidentified Positives”: Positives Detected in the Screening Step but Not Identified by LC-TOFMS Accurate Mass Analysis

cambendazole	303.0861	303.09102	15 (5 mDa)	no
difenoxuron	287.0906	287.13901	>100 (>50 mDa)	no
fluometuron	233.0428	233.08962	>100 (>40 mDa)	no

^a A total of three compounds were detected in the screening step but rejected after the accurate mass analysis step.

Table 4. Screening and Identification by LC-TOFMS of 15 Target Compounds in a Spiked Lemon Extract Fortified at 0.2 mg kg⁻¹ Level^a

pesticide	m/z_{exptl}	$m/z_{\text{theoretical}}$	(ppm)	confirmation
butocarboxin	213.0667	213.06682	0.6	yes
chloridazon	222.0426	222.04286	1.2	yes
chlorotoluron	213.0794	213.07891	2.3	yes
diazinon	305.1085	306.10832	0.6	yes
dichlofluanid	332.9704	332.96958	2.4	yes
fluroxypir	254.9735	254.9734	0.4	yes
imazalil	297.0565	297.05557	3.0	yes
ioxynil	371.8376	371.83769	0.3	yes
lenacil	235.1440	235.1441	0.4	yes
linuron	249.0192	249.0192	<0.1	yes
malathion	331.0437	331.04334	1.1	yes
metamitron	203.0928	203.09273	0.3	yes
methidathion	324.9509	324.95108	0.6	yes
prometryn	242.1433	242.14339	0.4	yes

“Unidentified Positives”: Positives Detected in the Screening Step but Not Identified by LC-TOFMS Accurate Mass Analysis

cambendazole	303.0499	303.09102	>100 (40 mDa)	no
cyromazine	167.0843	167.10397	>100 (20 mDa)	no
dimethomorph	388.1823	388.13101	>100 (50 mDa)	no
fluometuron	233.1542	233.08962	>100 (60 mDa)	no
monolinuron	215.0681	233.0580	50 (10 mDa)	no

^a Five compounds were detected in the screening step but rejected after accurate mass analysis step.

Table 5. Analytical Parameters of LC-MS/MS Method Using a Hybrid Triple Quadrupole Linear Ion Trap Instrument: LOQs and Linearity Obtained Using a Pepper Matrix, Comparison of LODs Obtained by LC-TOFMS and LC-MS/MS

pesticide	LOQ ($\mu\text{g}, \text{kg}^{-1}$)	linearity equations	R^2	LC-MS/MS	LC-TOFMS
cyromazine	10	$y = (2.69 \times 10^3)x + (3.46 \times 10^4)$	0.997	5	3
butoxycarboxin	15	$y = 303x + (4.49 \times 10^3)$	0.997	10	25
carbendazim	1	$y = (9.66 \times 10^3)x + (9.52 \times 10^4)$	0.998	0.5	3
thiabendazole	1.5	$y = (1.24 \times 10^4)x + (2.12 \times 10^5)$	0.997	0.5	3
oxamyl	20	$y = 72.6x + 536$	0.998	10	16
aldicarb sulfone	8	$y = 813x + (2.55 \times 10^3)$	0.998	3	35
nitenpyram	8	$y = 475x + 394$	0.999	1	12
methomyl	3.5	$y = (6.81 \times 10^3)x + (9.55 \times 10^4)$	0.998	1	10
chloridazon	3	$y = (3.3 \times 10^3)x + (1.02 \times 10^4)$	0.999	0.9	1.2
thiametoxam	5	$y = (1.48 \times 10^3)x + (2.34 \times 10^3)$	0.997	2.5	2
methiocarb sulfoxide	3.6	$y = (1.08 \times 10^4)x + (1.61 \times 10^4)$	0.999	1	10
metamitron	5	$y = (4.72 \times 10^3)x + (6.44 \times 10^3)$	0.997	1.2	0.6
cambendazole	1	$y = (1.84 \times 10^4)x + (4.96 \times 10^4)$	0.999	0.1	1
imidacloprid	3	$y = (1.84 \times 10^3)x + (8.9 \times 10^3)$	0.997	1	4.5
oxfendazole	0.7	$y = (2.13 \times 10^4)x + (1.13 \times 10^4)$	0.999	0.3	0.5
dimethoate	1	$y = (6.23 \times 10^3)x + (2.75 \times 10^3)$	0.999	0.1	9
acetamiprid	0.3	$y = (1.10 \times 10^4)x + (8.95 \times 10^4)$	0.997	0.1	3
cymoxanil	20	$y = 694x + (2.49 \times 10^3)$	0.997	6.6	30
albendazole	0.5	$y = (4.86 \times 10^4)x + (1.21 \times 10^5)$	0.999	0.1	0.5
butocarboxin	4	$y = (2.25 \times 10^3)x + (1.64 \times 10^4)$	0.998	2.5	4.5
methiocarb sulfone	18	$y = (1.74 \times 10^3)x + (1.74 \times 10^3)$	0.998	10	15
thiacloprid	1	$y = (4.28 \times 10^3)x + (1.32 \times 10^4)$	0.998	0.3	3
imazalil	1.3	$y = (8.24 \times 10^3)x + (5.15 \times 10^4)$	0.999	0.1	0.4
mebendazole	0.4	$y = (2.54 \times 10^4)x + (9.68 \times 10^4)$	0.999	0.1	0.45
aldicarb	7	$y = 342x + (4.54 \times 10^3)$	0.998	2	24
oxadixyl	2	$y = (6.07 \times 10^3)x + (2.54 \times 10^5)$	0.997	1	1.8
simazine	0.2	$y = (1.27 \times 10^4)x + (8.86 \times 10^4)$	0.998	0.05	1.2
fluroxypyr	10	$y = 418x + (4.49 \times 10^3)$	0.998	5	15
monuron	3.5	$y = (1.35 \times 10^4)x + (7.97 \times 10^4)$	0.998	1	0.9
lenacil	3.8	$y = (2.71 \times 10^3)x + (-1.15 \times 10^4)$	0.998	1	9
pyrimethanil	1.5	$y = (1.15 \times 10^4)x + (1.99 \times 10^3)$	0.999	0.4	0.18
spiroxamine	0.3	$y = (1.02 \times 10^5)x + (2.49 \times 10^5)$	0.999	0.05	0.18
ethoxyquin	2.2	$y = (9.05 \times 10^3)x + (2.14 \times 10^4)$	0.997	0.7	0.6
prometryn	0.3	$y = (3.05 \times 10^4)x + (3.98 \times 10^5)$	0.997	0.05	0.06
fenbendazole	0.4	$y = (6.25 \times 10^4)x + (2.8 \times 10^5)$	0.999	0.1	0.3
carbofuran	0.6	$y = (2.28 \times 10^4)x + (3.57 \times 10^5)$	0.998	0.07	6
chlorotoluron	1.4	$y = (1.07 \times 10^4)x + (5.55 \times 10^4)$	0.997	0.4	1.2
bendiocarb	3	$y = (2.2 \times 10^3)x + (1.68 \times 10^4)$	0.998	1	20
spinosyn A	0.3	$y = (1.12 \times 10^3)x + (1.75 \times 10^3)$	0.999	0.1	0.6
fluometuron	0.5	$y = (8.98 \times 10^3)x + (1.73 \times 10^4)$	0.999	0.1	0.9
atrazine	0.8	$y = (5.92 \times 10^4)x + (2.07 \times 10^5)$	0.999	0.1	0.5
miconazole	1.2	$y = (2.73 \times 10^4)x + (7.03 \times 10^4)$	0.999	0.1	1.8
metalaxyl	2	$y = (9.46 \times 10^3)x + (6.88 \times 10^4)$	0.999	0.6	0.6
isoproturon	1	$y = (1.11 \times 10^4)x + (3.79 \times 10^4)$	0.998	0.3	0.12
difenoxuron	0.8	$y = (1.49 \times 10^4)x + (1.34 \times 10^5)$	0.998	0.1	0.6
diuron	1.3	$y = (4.49 \times 10^3)x + (5.49 \times 10^4)$	0.998	0.5	1.5
monolinuron	2.5	$y = (3.68 \times 10^3)x + (2.02 \times 10^3)$	0.999	1	3
ethiofencarb	2	$y = (1.15 \times 10^4)x + (1.64 \times 10^5)$	0.998	1	9
spinosyn D	2.5	$y = (4.48 \times 10^3)x + (2.55 \times 10^4)$	0.997	1.5	0.45
metobromuron	3	$y = (3.50 \times 10^3)x + (-9.42 \times 10^3)$	0.999	1	4.5
dimethomorph	0.6	$y = (8.76 \times 10^3)x + (3.06 \times 10^3)$	0.997	0.1	3
flazasulfuron	2.5	$y = (3.22 \times 10^4)x + (-1.5 \times 10^5)$	0.999	1	0.6
prochloraz	2.2	$y = (2.69 \times 10^3)x + (2.96 \times 10^4)$	0.997	1	0.9
propazine	0.15	$y = (7.6 \times 10^4)x + (3.85 \times 10^5)$	0.999	0.04	0.12
cyproconazole	0.7	$y = (2.87 \times 10^4)x + (1.6 \times 10^5)$	0.998	0.1	0.6
methiocarb	1.2	$y = (4.92 \times 10^3)x + (2.32 \times 10^5)$	0.999	0.35	24
terbutylazine	0.04	$y = 604x + (3.21 \times 10^3)$	0.999	0.01	0.9
chloroxuron	0.25	$y = (2.1 \times 10^4)x + (1.18 \times 10^5)$	0.997	0.1	1.2
bromuconazole	0.5	$y = (8.98 \times 10^3)x + (4.23 \times 10^4)$	0.999	0.3	3
linuron	3.3	$y = (2.62 \times 10^3)x + (2.11 \times 10^4)$	0.998	1	3
methidathion	0.5	$y = (2.71 \times 10^3)x + (2.31 \times 10^4)$	0.997	0.1	15
fenamiphos	0.5	$y = (4.51 \times 10^4)x + (1.4 \times 10^5)$	0.999	0.1	3
chlorbromuron	3	$y = (3.18 \times 10^3)x + (-6.22 \times 10^3)$	0.999	0.6	6
azoxystrobin	0.1	$y = (2.89 \times 10^4)x + (3.52 \times 10^5)$	0.998	0.05	0.6
promecarb	0.3	$y = (3.35 \times 10^4)x + (2.15 \times 10^5)$	0.999	0.1	1.5
tebuconazole	1	$y = (6.34 \times 10^4)x + (-2.13 \times 10^4)$	0.999	0.25	3
diflubenzuron	3.2	$y = 688x + (-5.08 \times 10^3)$	0.998	1	15
iprodione	16	$y = 409x + (2.19 \times 10^3)$	0.998	5	18
triflumizol	0.5	$y = (2.11 \times 10^4)x + (1.72 \times 10^5)$	0.999	0.1	0.9
malathion	2.8	$y = (5.64 \times 10^3)x + (4.15 \times 10^4)$	0.997	0.8	2.4
neburon	2.6	$y = (5.33 \times 10^3)x + (6.29 \times 10^4)$	0.998	1	0.9
vinclozolin	16.6	$y = 383x + (3.45 \times 10^3)$	0.997	5	24

triflumuron	1	$y = (7.52 \times 10^3)x + (6.14 \times 10^4)$	0.999	0.5	12
dichlofluanid	1.8	$y = 463x + 972$	0.998	0.5	30
hexaflumuron	5	$y = (3.66 \times 10^3)x + (2.13 \times 10^4)$	0.999	1	9
buprofezin	0.3	$y = (1.63 \times 10^4)x + (5.54 \times 10^4)$	0.999	0.05	0.9
diazinon	0.1	$y = (4.31 \times 10^5)x + (2.23 \times 10^6)$	0.999	0.03	0.3
teflubenzuron	3.7	$y = 995x + (4.55 \times 10^3)$	0.999	1	12
lufenuron	18	$y = 589x + (8.31 \times 10^3)$	0.999	5	7.5
pyriproxyfen	0.05	$y = (2.35 \times 10^5)x + (1.56 \times 10^6)$	0.998	0.01	0.15
flufenoxuron	2.6	$y = (8.11 \times 10^3)x + (5.23 \times 10^3)$	0.999	0.8	6

Table 6. Application to Real Samples

compound detected	t _R (min) expected	t _R (min) exptl	Peak area counts x 10 ⁴	m/z ^{calcd}	m/z ^{exptl}	error (ppm)	identificat ion LC-TOFMS	Confirmation LC-MS/MS And Quantitation (µg kg ⁻¹)
carbendazim	7.34	7.30	47.5	192.07675	192.0765	1.3	yes	49.7
ethoxyquin	20.01	19.98	63.8	218.15394	218.1541	0.7	yes	6.7
imazalil	17.72	17.78	1350	297.05557	297.0561	1.7	yes	79.2
imazalil-met	14.49	14.42	8.82	257.02429	257.0236	2.7	yes	1.7 ^a
malathion	25.33	25.32	1.84	353.0256	353.0239	4.8	yes	10.2
lenacil	19.20	19.22	1.48	235.1441	235.1026	>10	no	
thiacloprid	17.78	17.83	2.42	253.03092	253.0305	1.6	yes	0.3
thiofanox sulfone	16.38	16.42	1.49	251.10600	251.1645	>10	no	
thiabendazole	9.00	9.04	2.33	202.04334	202.0439	2.7	yes	1.27
Pear No. 22078								
albendazole	17.86	17.71	10.2	266.09577	266.1430	>10	no	
aldicarb sulfone	11.35	10.75	3.37	223.0747	223.0561	>10	no	
carbendazim	7.33	7.30	12.7	192.07675	192.0771	1.8	yes	1.1
ethoxyquin	20.01	20.07	1850	218.15394	218.1539	0.2	yes	10.0
imazalil	17.72	17.71	4820	297.05557	297.0553	0.9	yes	297.3
imazalil-met	14.49	14.42	182	257.02429	257.0240	1.1	yes	27.5 ^a
tebuconazole	24.50	24.54	269	308.15241	308.1525	0.3	yes	12.8
thiabendazole	9.00	8.98	71.3	202.04334	202.0434	0.3	yes	9.1
Grapes No. 2733								
azoxystrobin	24.07	24.02	236	404.12409	404.1237	1.0	yes	19.4
cambendazole	14.88	14.77	21.2	303.09102	303.0511	>10	no	
carbendazim	7.34	7.31	57.3	192.07675	192.0772	2.3	yes	1.5
oxfendazole	15.54	15.58	1.04	316.07503	316.0642	>10	no	
thiabendazole	9.00	9.01	12.9	202.04334	404.1237	0.7	yes	5.2

^a Quantitation by LC-TOFMS.